

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
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Evaluation Report for

TEBT-2023-0007

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Collection of Time Activity Data to Support Exposure Assessment: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map
Submission Reference	TEBT-2023-0007
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley, ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Evaluators	Seneca Fitch, ORCID 0000-0001-9788-5973 Plus 2 anonymous reviewers
Submission Type	Secondary Study Protocol ▾
Preprint DOI	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8370525
Status	Accepted ▾
Evaluation Date	30 Mar 2024
Evaluation Round	Acceptance report
Recommendation	Accept ▾
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	The authors have responded satisfactorily to the reviewers' comments and the manuscript is therefore acceptable for publication.

Acceptance Report

This manuscript has been accepted for publication in *Evidence-Based Toxicology* by the handling editor after assessment in one round of editorial triage and two rounds of peer-review. Reviewers agree that an evidence map of this type could be a valuable contribution to the Time Activity Data (TAD) literature.

During triage, the handling editor had questions about whether the map would capture all the potentially eligible evidence that is relevant to its goals, and whether the coding and data storage methods were adequate for the goals of the map. These questions were resolved through revision and provision of a pilot database of training data, after which the manuscript was advanced to peer-review.

In the first round of peer-review, the major revisions related to improving the fit between the planned methods and the overarching goal of the mapping exercise. These were to address concerns that the evidence map risked overlooking behavioural data that is not currently well-recognised as TAD but would be of high relevance to the map's objectives.

In the second round of peer-review, further recommended revisions were minor and primarily related to the framing definition for TAD. In particular, this concerned a potential mismatch between the authors' chosen definition and the definition used by the target community of the evidence map, that could potentially limit the impact and utility of the map's findings. The handling editor accepted the authors' clarifications and revisions.

The full set of evaluation reports for this manuscript can be accessed at:

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10007611>

Note from the Handling Editor: I noticed in completing this acceptance report that my comments in follow-up to round one of triage ([here](#)) were not adequately communicated to the authors. I apologise for this issue. In these comments, I made some recommendations for how abstracted and coded data could be stored in the planned database. In my opinion, these issues are not critical to the acceptability of the protocol but may affect the integrity and utility of the final database. As such, I still recommend these issues be taken into account by the authors, but I do not think it would be appropriate to delay data collection by insisting on them being addressed before acceptance of the protocol.

Note about EBT's protocol assessment process: The EBT protocol assessment process evaluates a submitted protocol for demonstrating that, if followed, enough scientific work would be done that the relevant community (as represented by the peer-reviewers) would consider the anticipated study to be a unit of contribution to the scientific literature.

The first stage of assessment is Editorial Triage, where the Handling Editor assesses a protocol for compliance with EBT's open science standards. Standards-compliant protocols go to peer-review, where usually three or four reviewers provide comments about how the protocol could or should be modified, to make the planned study the best contribution to the literature that it can realistically be. These comments are aggregated by the Handling Editor into an Evaluation Report (this document).

If necessary, the authors, reviewers, and Handling Editor then discuss asynchronously the evaluation report and attempt to come to consensus on the most appropriate way to modify the protocol, through a combination of one or more of planning additional experimental work, modifying the data analysis plan, and revising how the research is described.

If necessary, a revised protocol is re-reviewed, further discussions held, and changes made, until the Handling Editor, authors, and peer-reviewers are satisfied that enough work has been done for the protocol to count as an Accepted Contribution to the literature. At this point the protocol is formally published in the journal.